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Analyzing Feminist Characteristic of Main Character Enola In The 2020 Movie "Enola Holmes" By Nancy Springer

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Abstrak

This research examines how feminism was depicted in the 18th century within the film Enola Holmes by Nancy Springer. It explores how Enola, the main character, challenges conventional gender norms by her behaviors, embodying feminist principles and going against the societal norms for women during that period. Using a qualitative descriptive research approach, the study examines how the film depicts Enola's defiance of traditional norms like marriage and household duties, and her quest for independence and empowerment. The study also explores the wider social and historical background of the feminist movement in the 18th century, emphasizing gender equality and women's rights. By following Enola's journey, the movie explores feminist topics, providing insights on historical and current battles for gender parity. The results emphasize the changing depiction of females in movies, with Enola Holmes demonstrating how feminist ideas can be integrated into popular stories. In the end, the research highlights the importance of representation in questioning gender norms and promoting social change.

Keywords: *Feminism, Linguistics, Sociolinguistics.*

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INTRODUCTION

Communication originates from the use of language, which serves as the foundation for conveying thoughts, emotions, and information. When language is present in a society, the field of linguistics naturally comes into play to study its structure, evolution, and usage. Linguistics encompasses various branches that delve into different aspects of language, including pragmatics, semantics, and sociolinguistics. Each of these branches focuses on specific elements of communication and language usage within various social contexts. The field of pragmatics, for example, explores how language is used to achieve certain goals and communicate effectively in different situations. Semantics, on the other hand, examines the meanings of words and how they are interpreted in various contexts.

Sociolinguistics, meanwhile, investigates the relationship between language and society, including how language is used to express social identity and interact with others. These branches of linguistics provide valuable insights into the complex nature of language and communication. In the past, opera was well-known, but now movies have taken its place as a popular form of entertainment. Movies are considered a replacement for opera because they are easier to access by the general public. Unlike opera, which requires people to physically attend a performance, movies can be easily watched on mobile phones, making them more convenient for everyone.

A movie can serve as a prime illustration of sociolinguistics due to the way it incorporates a blend of societal concerns and the study of language. This makes movies a rich source of analysis for researchers in the field. Movies have evolved significantly from the early days of cinema, with movie makers exploring a wide variety of genres to cater to different audience preferences. These genres range from action-packed thrillers to heartwarming romances and everything in between. One such example of a modern movie that delves into feminist themes is "Enola Holmes" based on a novel by Nancy Springer.

The movie industry has come a long way in terms of diversity and representation. Directors and writers are constantly pushing boundaries and exploring new narratives that reflect the

complexities of the human experience. "Enola Holmes" is a prime example of how contemporary movies are addressing important social issues, such as gender equality and empowerment.

The portrayal of strong, independent female characters in movies like "Enola Holmes" is a positive step towards challenging traditional gender roles in storytelling. By presenting complex and multidimensional female leads, movie makers are contributing to a more inclusive and diverse cinematic landscape. "Feminism" in cinema is not limited to just one type of story or character. It can manifest in various ways, from subtle nuances in dialogue to overt statements on gender inequality. In the case of "Enola Holmes," the movie's protagonist embodies feminist ideals by defying societal expectations and asserting her independence.

The success of movies like "Enola Holmes" also highlights the growing demand for diverse and empowering narratives in entertainment. Audiences are increasingly drawn to stories that champion social justice and challenge established norms, making it imperative for movie makers to continue exploring feminist themes in their work.

Feminists have consistently faced challenges in advocating for women's rights, including equal pay for equal work in comparison to men. They are also focused on promoting gender equality. Advocates for women's rights, particularly feminists, have encountered numerous obstacles in their efforts to achieve equality, such as fighting for equitable pay that is commensurate with that of their male counterparts. Furthermore, their primary objective is to advance the principles of gender equality and empower women in society.

The movie "Enola Holmes" by Nancy Springer offers a rich source for analysis, especially highlighting the challenges faced by women to fight for their rights in the 18th century. Below are several Statements of Problem that will be examined in more detail:

1. What makes Enola's actions in the movie "Enola Holmes" by Nancy Springer seen as unusual given the societal expectations for women during that period?
2. How did Enola's feminist attitude cause issues during that period?

In order to offer a comprehensive understanding of the feminist movement in the 18th century, it is crucial to delve deeper into the historical background that forms the foundation for Nancy Springer's movie "Enola Holmes." Understanding the societal norms and gender roles of that era is essential in order to grasp the significance of the feminist themes portrayed in the movie.

The historical context of the 18th century provides a rich tapestry of events and beliefs that shaped the feminist movement of the time. By examining the social, political, and cultural landscape of that period, one can gain a deeper appreciation for the challenges faced by women and the strides made towards gender equality. "Enola Holmes" serves as a window into the struggles and triumphs of women during the 18th century, shedding light on the complexities of the feminist movement.

The feminist themes in "Enola Holmes" are not just a reflection of the past but also a commentary on the present, highlighting the ongoing struggle for gender equality. The movie challenges traditional gender norms and empowers viewers to question social constructs that limit the potential of women. Through the character of Enola, audiences are inspired to break free from the constraints of patriarchy and forge their own paths.

The feminist themes in "Enola Holmes" resonate with contemporary audiences, underscoring the importance of gender equality and women's empowerment in today's society. Through its exploration of the past, the movie encourages viewers to reflect on the progress that has been made and the work that still needs to be done in the fight for gender equality.

The character of Enola serves as a beacon of hope and inspiration for women everywhere, encouraging them to embrace their autonomy and challenge societal norms. Overall, "Enola Holmes" offers a compelling portrayal of the feminist movement in the 18th century, inviting audiences to contemplate the enduring relevance of gender equality and female empowerment.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Linguistics

According to (Oviogun & Veerdee, 2020), Linguistics is often called general linguistics, meaning that linguistics does not only investigate one language, but linguistics concerns language in general. (Leivada & Murphy, 2021) also quote that Linguistics is a relatively young field. According to (Saleh Alduais, 2012), the study of language has been considerably developed to the extent some

linguists have started to seriously but arguably consider it as a [science] rather than a branch of (Humanities).

Sociolinguistics

According to (Sosyolinguistiği et al., n.d.), There is a branch of linguistics that deals with these social variations and it is called “sociolinguistics”. According to (Cong, 2023), The research achievements of sociolinguistics play a positive and promoting role in the development of language, demonstrating the social attributes of language, enriching research methods, promoting the standardized development of language, accelerating the language acquisition process, improving the level of language teaching, and enhancing language communication abilities, etc. According to (Nasution et al., 2019), Sociolinguistics is a branch of linguistics that specifically examines the use of language in society.

Feminist

According to (Aryaa et al., n.d.), A feminist is ‘a person who supports the belief that women should have the same rights and opportunities as men’. According to (Crossman, 2018), Feminist theory is a major branch of theory within sociology that shifts its assumptions, analytic lens, and topical focus away from the male viewpoint and experience and toward that of women. According to (Lemke, 2016), feminist organizations are responsible for prompting local, national, and international policies that address sexual harassment, rape, gender discrimination, and female poverty among other major social issues.

Relevant Studies

Researchers with similar objectives but varying methodologies have conducted studies on the topic. The following is a compilation of relevant articles on the subject:

1. Gender Stereotypes in Enola Holmes: a Film Analysis of The Main Character by (Azis & Sunra, 2022) from *ELITERATE: Journal of English Linguistics and Literature Studies*
2. Emancipation of Women Represented by The Main Character Enola in The Movie "Enola Holmes" by (Utami & Wahyuni, 2022) from *Jurnal Pendidikan Profesi Guru*.
3. Characterization of Enola Holmes in The Case of The Missing Marquess: A Study of Liberal Feminism by (Sakinah & Setyorini, 2022) from *PHILOLOGY Journal of English Language and Literature*.

Research Method

The researcher chose to employ the qualitative descriptive research approach to thoroughly examine the representation of feminism in Nancy Springer's movie "Enola Holmes" through the character of Enola Holmes. This particular research method involves a detailed analysis of the various aspects of feminism portrayed in the movie, focusing on how they are embodied and represented by the central character. By utilizing this approach, the researcher aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the nuances and complexities of feminism as depicted in the movie.

Researchers have the opportunity to gain insight into the historical context of the feminist during the time period depicted in the movie "Enola Holmes" by Nancy Springer. Below are the stages of the data research process outlined in this study:

1. Researchers repeatedly viewed the movie "Enola Holmes" as part of their study. The purpose of this continuous viewing was to examine the portrayal of women during that historical period.
2. Researchers documented the how women act during that particular year.
3. Researchers embarked on an extensive investigation into the history of feminists in order to analyze their previous societal roles. The study specifically honed in on the various employment opportunities available to women during the 18th century.
4. Researchers gather research findings as well as data contained within this study.
5. Researchers initiated the consolidation of the findings derived from the collected data, as well as the outcomes of the analysis conducted on Nancy Springer's movie "Enola Holmes."

RESULT AND DISCUSSION**What makes Enola's actions in the movie "Enola Holmes" by Nancy Springer seen as unusual given the societal expectations for women during that period?**

Enola's behaviour is considered strange because it goes against the typical norms for women during that time. Pictures 1, 2, and 3 illustrate Enola's unique behaviour compared to other women of her era.

1) During the first scene (Picture 1), Mycroft is in disbelief at what he observes in the room.

Picture 1 shows Mycroft asking about something

The picture above depicts Mycroft inquiring about something that he finds unbelievable. A woman rarely participates in tennis, however, when Enola and her mother do, she senses that it goes against societal expectations for women.

Mycroft : *What is this?*

Enola : *Tennis? Mother says I'm getting quite proficient.*

Enola Holmes movie (Duration 07:29-07:54)

The next part of the scene portrays Enola and her mother playing tennis in the same room. Mycroft then noticed the wall being used as the scoring board. Upon witnessing this, Mycroft's anger intensified as he struggled to comprehend the events unfolding in his own home. 2 women who were not acting appropriately during that period. During that period, women were expected to be elegant like swans, but it seemed that their mother and sister acted differently. Mycroft finds his mother and sister's behaviour unacceptable.

2) In the following scene (Picture 2), Enola and her mother engage in physical training by practicing combat techniques.

Picture 2 Enola and her mother are seen practicing self-defense techniques together.

The picture above illustrates how Enola's mother taught her self-defence at a young age in order to empower Enola to protect herself in dangerous situations. Enola, who had never faced danger before, struggled to battle that individual. Enola felt fortunate to have learned self-defence from her mother, as it enabled her to evade those who were after her.

Enola : *We'd start with history. She always said...*

Eudoria : *Historical perspective is the only way to begin a day.*

Enola : *Then we'd lunch, and I'd work on my physics. Then after lunch, I'd focus on fitness...*

Eudoria : *Got you!*

Enola : ...followed by fight combat.

Eudoria : *Hands up! Hands up! Up! Up again. Come on.*

Enola Holmes movie (Duration 51:08-51:54)

This scene shows Enola's childhood habits, beginning with studying history and physics, having lunch, and then practicing self-defence by sparring with her mother. Engaging in a battle with her mother gave Enola the courage to engage in another fight.

3) In the final scene (Picture 3), Enola was unsure of how to do embroidery.

Picture 3 Enola is watching her classmate to learn how to do embroidery.

The image above displays Enola attempting to do embroidery, but her embroidered result did not match that of her classmate. Enola is feeling unusual as she believes she was doing the same thing as her classmate, but her outcome did not turn out as well as her classmate's.

Miss Harrison : *Act, think, be as we tell you, and you'll become acceptable wives and responsible mothers.*

Enola Holmes movie (Duration 1:20:26-1:20:35)

the following scene, Enola behaves in a manner that sets her apart from the other girls at school. Enola continues to eat her food hunched over, while the girls laugh at her. Despite being ridiculed, Enola fights back by purposefully spilling her food on the girl who was mocking her. Her mother taught him well; just because someone behaves differently, it doesn't give others the right to ridicule him.

How did Enola's feminist attitude cause issues during that period?

During that period, women were commonly pressure to adhere to traditional expectations: getting married, becoming mothers, and focusing on household duties. Despite this, Enola rebels against these limitations and shows a modern, self-reliant mindset that goes against the gender expectations of the time. Enola's feminist attitude is reflected in pictures 4, 5, and 6 as she elicits varied reactions from each character in the film.

1) In the opening scene, picture 4, Enola refuses to get married.

Picture 4 Enola's response is shown when Mycroft mentions marriage.

The picture above depicts Enola's reaction to Mycroft bringing up marriage. Mycroft also criticizes Enola for being uneducated as she only wears his undergarments. Enola flees from Miss Harrison after insulting her by refusing to attend her school.

Enola : *Let me remain happy. I am happy here.*

Mycroft : *You are a young woman now, Enola. You need an education.*

Enola : *Test me on anything you think I need to know to be sufficient for this world.*

Mycroft: *If she taught you so well, you wouldn't be standing in your undergarments in front of me. You have no hope of making a husband in your current state.*

Enola : *I don't want a husband!*

Mycroft : *And that is another thing you need to have educated out of you.*

Enola Holmes movie (Duration 14:01-14:22)

This scene highlights Enola's desire to break free from traditional gender roles and stereotypes. She craved independence and equality for women, seeking to have the same opportunities and experiences as men. This led her to seek Sherlock Holmes as a guardian instead of his brother, Mycroft.

2) In the next scene, picture 5, Enola meets Lady Tewkesbury, Marchioness of Basilwether.

Picture 5 Lady Tewkesbury, Marchioness of Basilwether, was skeptical of Enola's words.

The picture shows Enola offering to assist Lady Tewkesbury in finding her son, but initially Lady Tewkesbury was skeptical of Enola's claims. However, when Enola mentioned she works for Sherlock Holmes, Lady Tewkesbury's attitude towards her changed.

Enola : *I believe I can help you.*

Lady Tewkesbury : *You are a reporter for one of those dirty newspapers.*

Enola : *I am a lady detective.*

Lady Tewkesbury : *Please leave, before we make you leave.*

Enola : *I work for Sherlock Holmes. I...I'm His assistant. He sends me ahead of time to prepare the ground.*

Enola Holmes movie (Duration 57:15-58:06)

In the upcoming scene, Lady Tewkesbury continues to question Enola, though she has started to consider the possibility that Sherlock Holmes may have actually sent her. However, her doubts are reignited when another detective arrives, claiming to be a close friend of Sherlock Holmes. Ultimately, Lady Tewkesbury dismissed both of them.

3) In the final scene, Picture 6, Lestrade shows interest in Enola, Sherlock Holmes' sister.

Picture 6 Lestrade is amazed by Enola, Sherlock Holmes' sister.

The image shows Lestrade's surprise when Enola, the girl he apprehended for Mycroft, managed to crack the Marquess Case before Sherlock Holmes could. Lestrade views Enola as lacking education, according to Mycroft, but Enola ends up proving herself by solving the Marquess Case.

Sherlock Holmes : *The medals on his chest. He wasn't in the country when the boy's father was killed, rather serving in the Afghan war. It's always there, the truth.*

Lestrade : *Yeah.*

Sherlock Holmes : *You just need to look for it.*

Lestrade : *Second question. How did your sister get there before ya?*

Sherlock Holmes : *I'm sorry?*

Enola Holmes movie (Duration 1:44:57-1:45:27)

In the following scene, Sherlock Holmes admires Enola for proving that she is intelligent and capable of being a detective like his brother. It is uncommon for women to achieve equal recognition in the workplace as men, but Enola accomplished it through her dedication. Following that, Lady Tewksbury paid Enola for locating her son.

CONCLUSION

Enola behaves in the manner her mother instructed, unafraid and willing to defend others. Enola is attempting to emulate her mother's actions, but a particular incident leads her to believe her mother is indeed a dangerous woman, as Mycroft had claimed. However, when Enola finally confronts her mother and questions why she engages in perilous activities, her mother explains that sometimes one must make a commotion in order for their intentions to be acknowledged. Enola's mother's actions aim to achieve gender equality in all areas, and if men understand her intentions, they may label her as a feminist. Enola's mother engages in the risky action in a covert manner.

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